

Relation between the Lattice Energy and Melting Point of some Crystalline Substances. Part IX. Oxides and Chlorides of Lanthanides

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The approximate proportionality between the lattice energy, $-U_o$, and the corresponding absolute melting point, T_m , among the members of a set of simple and similar substances, appears to be well-established^{1,2}. The same is also true for the absolute boiling point T_b i.e., $-U_o/T_b \approx \text{constant}$, although this constancy is not very impressive and many substances decompose before reaching the boiling point. The oxides and chlorides of the lanthanide elements, have been examined in the present note, as these are expected to form a closely related set of similar substances.

For some oxides and most of the chlorides of these elements $-U_o$, T_m and T_b have been given in the literature^{3,4}. From these values for the oxides, the ratio, $-U_o/T_m$, has been calculated in different cases and is given in Table I.

TABLE I

Oxide*	$-U_o$ (Kcal)	T_m (°K)	$-U_o/T_m$
La_2O_3	3011	2599	1.16
Ce_2O_3	3057	2235	1.37
Pr_2O_3	3081	2540**	—
Nd_2O_3	3081	2540**	—
Pm_2O_3	—	—	—
Sm_2O_3	3104	2579	1.21
Eu_2O_3	3118	2600**	—
Gd_2O_3	3138	2603	1.21
Tb_2O_3	—	—	—
Dy_2O_3	3182	2613	1.22
Ho_2O_3	3200	2670**	—
Er_2O_3	3218	2680**	—
Tm_2O_3	3235	2700**	—
Yb_2O_3	3251	2710**	—
Lu_2O_3	3266	2720**	—

* Boiling points are not known.

** Estimated absolute melting points.

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As may be seen from Table I, the $-U_o/T_m$ is very nearly constant (i. e. ≈ 21), the maximum deviation being less than 5% except in Ce_2O_3 .

For many oxides, the melting points have not been determined although their lattice energies have been calculated^{3,4}. It is possible to make a fairly reasonable estimate of the melting point in different cases from the relation $-U_o/T_m$ i. e. ≈ 21 . The values of the absolute melting points, calculated on this basis, are given in Table I.

Table II gives the various parameters for the chlorides of the lanthanides. It may be observed that here again the ratios $-U_o/T_m$ and $-U_o/T_b$, are approximately constant for the whole set, their average values being, respectively, 1.04 and 0.57; the former appears to pass through a maximum and the latter, slightly increases with the atomic number although both the ratios are well within 10% of the respective average value.

TABLE II

Chloride	$-U_o(\text{Kcal})$	T_m ($^{\circ}\text{K}$)	T_b ($^{\circ}\text{K}$)	$-U_o/T_m$	$-U_o/T_b$
LaCl_3	1019	1125	2025	0.91	0.50
CeCl_3	1027	1075	2003	0.96	0.51
PrCl_3	1033	1049	1973	0.98	0.52
NdCl_3	1038	1033	1963	1.01	0.53
SmCl_3	1046	951	dec.	1.10	—
EuCl_3	1050	896	dec.	1.17	—
GdCl_3	1053	882	1853	1.19	0.57
TbCl_3	1036**	861	1823	—	—
DyCl_3	1071	927	{ 1773 1878**	1.16	—
HoCl_3	1078	991	1773	1.09	0.61
ErCl_3	1082	1047	1773	1.03	0.61
TmCl_3	1087	1094	1763	0.99	0.62
YbCl_3	1091	1127	dec.	0.97	—
LuCl_3	1092	1165	1753	0.94	0.62

**Estimated values.

The lattice energy, $-U_o$, of TbCl_3 could not be calculated theoretically due to unavailability of the required data³. One can, however, estimate its $-U_o$, with a fair degree of accuracy, from the principle of correspondence at the melting and boiling points¹ and using $-U_o/T_m \approx 1.04$ and $-U_o/T_b \approx 0.57$. The lattice energy of TbCl_3 , thus obtained, is about 1030 Kcal/mole. Similarly the absolute boiling point of DyCl_3 , should be about 1880°.